

Project BALAY: A NEEDS ASSESSMENT FOR BASIC LITERACY AMONG YOUNG AND ADULT INDIGENOUS PEOPLE

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ABSTRACT

Reading and writing skills are crucial for Indigenous communities as they preserve their unique cultures and traditions and aid in recording their language, stories, and historical knowledge. Additionally, they play a vital role in providing a platform for self-expression, allowing Indigenous voices to be heard, and advocating for their rights and interests. With this, the researchers were motivated to conduct the study to determine the basic literacy needs of young and adult Indigenous Peoples (IPs) which would serve as a basis for conducting needed training. This is descriptive research wherein 150 indigenous people from the selected Mangyan communities in Panaytayan, Mansalay, Oriental Mindoro were interviewed using the researchers' checklist to gather the needed data. Frequency and percentage were used in this study. According to the findings, it is evident that the participants have a considerable lack of reading and writing skills. Moreover, the IPs must receive proper training to master the fundamentals of reading and writing competencies. The researchers proposed creating a strategic plan to implement PROJECT BALAY – Basic Literacy for Young and Adult Indigenous people. The primary focus would be honing basic letter recognition skills and targeting reading comprehension and writing skills in older children.

Keywords: *needs assessment, Indigenous people, literacy, reading and writing skills, Panaytayan, Mansalay, Oriental Mindoro, Project BALAY*

INTRODUCTION

Literacy serves as the foundation for education, providing opportunities for personal growth, survival, safety, and stability. The ability to read, write, and comprehend written language is vital for success in all aspects of life - from academics to the workplace to everyday interactions. Developing strong literacy skills allows individuals to effectively communicate, access information, problem-solve, make informed decisions, and engage in community involvement.

Beyond these practical benefits, literacy also plays a crucial role in personal development, shaping individuals' understanding of societal norms and values. As noted by Abad (2020), it fosters human formation and empowers learners to embrace diverse cultures, appreciate literature and the arts, and sharpen critical thinking abilities. Ultimately, literacy opens doors to endless possibilities and enriching experiences.

In the Philippines, there is a deep appreciation for proficient reading and writing skills. As such, the country has wholeheartedly embraced initiatives to improve overall literacy levels, receiving enthusiastic support from both individuals and various organizations (Cristobal, 2015). The government and non-governmental entities alike have joined forces in pursuit of the Education for All (EFA) 2015 plan, which aims to make basic education accessible to all and revolutionize traditional educational practices that have primarily been limited to schools (UNESCO, 2015). This is evident in the enactment of DepEd Order 94 s.2009, which mandates the establishment of EFA division and regional committees to effectively work towards achieving global literacy goals. Likewise, the fourth Sustainable Development Goal of UNESCO places a strong emphasis on the quality of education. It aims to provide inclusive and fair access to education for all individuals, including Indigenous students from Indigenous communities (Rahim, et al. 2022). This not only ensures a high standard of education but also promotes lifelong learning opportunities for these students.

Moreover, the education of Indigenous Peoples (IPs) is held in high regard and receives significant attention in the Philippines. As reported by BusinessMirror (2017), the Department of Education (DepEd) remains committed to its Indigenous Peoples Education (IPEd) Program, actively working towards promoting culturally responsive education and integrating it into the K-12 curriculum. Unfortunately, despite these efforts to promote equality in education, prejudice, and marginalization persist among Indigenous communities (Abad, 2020).

The Indigenous Peoples (IPs) hold generations of collected wisdom within them as they weave a bright tapestry of cultures and customs worldwide. There are more than 17 million indigenous people, representing 110 ethnolinguistic groups in the Philippines (Camaya & Tamayo, 2018; Penaranda, 2019; Eduardo & Gabriel, 2021). Every group embodies a distinctive culture and language passed down from their ancestors (Bastida, Jr. et al, 2022). Bociaga (2020) mentioned that among these groups are the Mangyans, who reside on the island of Mindoro, with an estimated population of 100,000 to 280,000, making up 7.5% to 21% of Mindoro's total population. According to The Library of Congress Research Guide (2023), there are eight identified ethnic groups in the

Philippines, namely: Iraya, Alangan, Tadyawan, Tawbuid, Bangon, Buhid, Hanunuo, and Ratagnon. While commonly known as "Mangyan," only the Hanunuo tribe identifies with this term. It is worth noting as well that these indigenous groups each have their unique languages.

In Panaytayan, Mansalay in Oriental Mindoro resides a vibrant community of the Hanunuo tribes. These indigenous people, known for their rich cultural heritage and deep connection to the natural world, have called this region home for generations. Nevertheless, despite their rich history, there have been reports of illiteracy among the tribe members, attributed to a range of factors. As stated by Bamba, et al. (2021), there remain pockets of illiteracy among indigenous populations, particularly those living in secluded areas where traditional customs and values are still upheld. Unfortunately, these regions are situated far from the public schools, causing students to embark on a long and treacherous journey to receive a formal education. Not only that, but Paul, et al. (2013) also stressed that most of them face many barriers to education, brought on by unfavorable family environments, familial responsibilities including taking care of younger siblings, and poverty.

Given this premise, the researchers are driven to carry out a needs assessment study to gather essential data for the extension program that aims to improve the reading and writing skills of the youth and adults in the chosen Mangyan villages of Panaytayan, Mansalay, Oriental Mindoro. This initiative is crucial in enabling them to achieve economic independence and overall wellness, ultimately shaping them into responsible and thriving members of their community and society.

Research Objectives

The study aimed to determine the writing and reading needs of Indigenous People residing in the selected Mangyan Community in Panaytayan, Mansalay, Oriental Mindoro. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. determine the knowledge level of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 reading skills and reading comprehension.; and
 - 1.2 writing skills.
2. based on the findings of the study what intervention can be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive research method. The Descriptive research method involved determining, describing, and identifying key elements (Ethridge, 2004) to assess the knowledge level of the Mangyan Community in Panaytayan, Mansalay in Oriental Mindoro.

The respondents of the study were the 150 Indigenous people living in the four adapted Mangyan communities in Panaytayan, Mansalay, Oriental Mindoro of the Mindoro State University and LGU Mansalay namely: Calibang; Ether; Tanawan; and

Sinugbuhan. The respondents were taken purposively among the selected communities. The participants were personally approached and provided with a clear explanation of the study's goals. Additionally, before an interview takes place, participants are given a thorough understanding of their rights. They are informed about the purpose of collecting their personal information, how it will be utilized, and who will have access to it. This is all under Republic Act 10173, also known as the Data Privacy Act (DPA), to ensure the protection of the participants. In addition, the respondents are carefully selected based on specific criteria and willingly choose to be a part of the research. Data collection was completed as required.

The main data-gathering tool used for this study to determine the IPs' understanding of basic literacy was a checklist with two major parts. The first part was the survey asked about the reading skills of the respondents while the second part is to assess their writing skills. This checklist was read to the respondents and their responses were analyzed and interpreted.

The results were presented in tabular format using descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentage.

RESULTS

1. Knowledge level of the respondents in terms of:

Table 1. Knowledge level of the respondents in terms of basic reading skills and comprehension

Statements	CAN		CANNOT	
	F	%	F	%
1. Can you recognize the letters of the alphabet? <i>Makikilala mo ba ang mga titik ng alpabeto?</i>	48	32%	102	68%
2. Can you read the syllables? <i>Kaya mo bang basahin ang mga pantig?</i>	30	20%	120	80%
3. Can you read and understand the words? <i>Kaya mo bang basahin at unawain ang mga salita?</i>	18	12%	132	88%
4. Can you read and understand the sentences? <i>Kaya mo bang basahin at unawain ang mga pangungusap?</i>	10	7%	140	93%

Table 1 shows that out of 150 participants, only 48 (32%) can identify the letters of the alphabet, and 10 (7%) can comprehend sentences. On the other hand, the majority, 140 (93%), struggle with reading and comprehending sentences, followed by 132 (88%) who struggle with words, 120 (80%) with syllables, and 102 (68%) who are unable to recognize letters of the alphabet.

1.2 Writing skills

Table 2. Knowledge level of the respondents in terms of basic writing skills

WRITING	CAN		CANNOT	
	F	%	F	%
1. Can you write the letters of the alphabet? <i>Kaya mo bang isulat ang mga titik ng alpabeto?</i>	40	27%	110	73%
2. Can you write syllables? <i>Marunong ka bang magsulat ng mga pantig?</i>	34	23%	116	77%
3. Can you write words? <i>Marunong ka bang magsulat ng mga salita?</i>	28	19%	122	81%
4. Can you write sentences? <i>Marunong ka bang magsulat ng mga pangungusap?</i>	11	7%	139	93%

As indicated in Table 2, 40 participants (27%) could write the letters of the alphabet and only 11 (7%) could write sentences. The data clearly shows that a larger number of participants possess only basic letter-writing skills, rather than more advanced sentence-writing abilities. Conversely, most of them 139 (93%) cannot write sentences, 122 (81%) cannot write words, 116 (77%) cannot write syllables, and 110 (73%) cannot write the letters of the alphabet.

DISCUSSION

1. Knowledge level of the respondents in terms of:

1.1 Reading skills and comprehension

The finding implies that there are some participants with foundational letter recognition skills, but only a small number possess advanced reading comprehension abilities that go beyond basic letter recognition. Thus, the result indicates a potential gap in foundational literacy skills, as there appears to be a low percentage of individuals who can identify letters of the alphabet and an even lower percentage who can comprehend sentences. Shaili (2023) asserts that as children embark on the journey of learning to read and write, one crucial skill they must acquire is letter recognition. This foundational skill allows them to identify letters, enabling them to absorb new vocabulary and improve their reading flow swiftly and effortlessly. This is consistent with Lynch's (2020) claims that developing letter recognition is crucial for mastering reading skills. Without this fundamental ability, children face challenges in understanding letter sounds and identifying words. It becomes increasingly difficult for them to grasp the basics of reading when they are unable to recognize letters and their corresponding sounds.

On the other hand, the majority, 140 (93%), struggle with reading and comprehending sentences, followed by 132 (88%) who struggle with words, 120 (80%)

with syllables, and 102 (68%) who are unable to recognize letters of the alphabet. These findings suggest that this group faces significant challenges in their reading abilities across all levels, including letters, syllables, words, and sentence understanding. While sentences and word recognition appear to be the most troublesome areas overall, lower-level skills like letters and syllables are also problematic for a significant portion of the group. Overall, a significant portion of the group struggles with reading proficiency across all levels. According to, Llego (2022) one of the most common challenges faced by students when it comes to reading is trouble with decoding words, insufficient comprehension abilities, and limited fluency. Further, as cited by Totto and Ramos (2021) from the study of Sünbül et al. (2010) students who struggle with reading fluency and comprehension will have difficulty achieving success.

The data clearly show that the IPs need to learn how to read. Learning to read is crucial for Indigenous empowerment, self-determination, and the preservation of their cultural heritage in a changing world. To address this gap in the reading abilities of the respondents, educational initiatives and support programs could be an immense help in giving them strong foundational reading skills. According to Mesmer (2020), foundational reading skills are crucial for developing advanced literacy. As students improve their word recognition abilities, they are better equipped to understand complex ideas and vocabulary. Furthermore, the ELA/ELD Framework specifically acknowledges the importance of basic skills, or foundational reading skills, as a key teaching and learning principle. This is because having a strong foundation in reading is necessary for becoming independent with written language, as noted by Spycher (2017). This correlates to the ideas of Chamba and Ramirez-Avila (2021), that to become a proficient reader, one must possess five essential elements of reading instruction: phonemic awareness, phonics, word recognition, vocabulary, and comprehension. These elements work together to provide the necessary tools for developing strong reading skills and becoming an accomplished reader (Gunobgunob-Mirasol, 2019). At the same time, Philipps (2022) highlights the critical role that foundational reading skills play in a comprehensive reading program aimed at fostering proficient readers. She stresses the idea that individuals cannot fully comprehend various types of texts without a solid grasp of fundamental reading skills.

Moreover, to enhance the reading skills of IPs, they must develop strong reading comprehension. This fundamental aspect of reading should be approached holistically, as it pertains to all aspects of life (Caraig & Quimbo, 2022). Granda and Ramírez-Avila (2020) similarly define reading comprehension as a vital process that involves absorbing and understanding a text. By making connections between their prior knowledge and new information, readers can effectively comprehend and make meaning of the text.

Further, the findings bring to light a pervasive issue of inadequate education leading to low literacy rates among the participants. The severity of reading difficulties emphasizes the urgent need for intervention within this community. Comprehensive reading remediation initiatives and individualized literacy support may be essential in addressing these deficiencies. Failure to do so may result in persistent struggles that can impact an individual's entire life.

1.2 Writing skills

As indicated in Table 2, 40 participants (27%) could write the letters of the alphabet and only 11 (7%) could write sentences. The data clearly shows that a larger number of participants possess only basic letter-writing skills, rather than more advanced sentence-writing abilities. This demonstrates that letter writing is a fundamental skill that is typically learned earlier than the ability to construct sentences and paragraphs. The comparatively smaller percentage of individuals with sentence writing skills hints at potential deficiencies in the development of advanced writing proficiency.

Conversely, most of them 139 (93%) cannot write sentences, 122 (81%) cannot write words, 116 (77%) cannot write syllables, and 110 (73%) cannot write the letters of the alphabet. This indicates that a considerable percentage of the participants possess insufficient writing skills. This finding aligns with Graham, et al. 's (2016) research, examining the writing abilities of elementary students classified as struggling writers. The data revealed strikingly low scores, as only 3% of the students met or surpassed grade-level standards for writing proficiency. They concluded that numerous students are lacking basic writing skills, even at the elementary level. Further, writing is not just a skill, but a powerful tool for communication, self-expression, sharing information, and preserving history (Stone, 2023; Tewari, 2022). Yet, the presence of gaps in the writing proficiency of the respondents can greatly hinder their ability to effectively convey their ideas and connect with others.

The data thus underscores a disconcerting level of illiteracy challenges within the group, emphasizing the pressing need to delve into and resolve these concerns. Targeted interventions are likely necessary to enhance the literacy and writing skills of the respondents. Offering educational opportunities and training in basic writing skills or writing intervention programs to indigenous people is imperative in preserving their cultural heritage and promoting self-governance. Cabigao (2021) concluded in his study that by implementing a writing intervention program, learners can develop their basic writing skills and ultimately bridge any gaps in their learning. Likewise, he said that engaging and well-designed writing activities and exercises play a crucial role in helping learners enhance their fundamental writing skills.

Conclusions

The study revealed significant deficiencies in the reading and writing abilities of the participants. While many were able to identify letters and syllables, a considerable portion struggled with constructing words and sentences in both reading and writing. These findings indicate a pressing need for interventions catering to various skill levels, specifically addressing the gap between basic letter formation and word construction.

Recommendations

From the gathered data, the following recommendations are proposed: prioritizing fundamental skills such as phonemic awareness and phonics to enhance decoding and

word identification, potentially leading to improved reading fluency, comprehension, and writing proficiency

Furthermore, the researchers proposed the creation of a strategic plan to implement *PROJECT - BALAY – Basic Literacy for Young and Adults*. The primary focus would be on honing basic letter recognition skills, while also targeting reading comprehension and writing skills in older children. This strategic plan aims to address the gaps in literacy skills and promote lifelong learning. The implementation process will commence with teaching the fundamentals of identifying, tracing, and comprehending letters of the alphabet, utilizing well-designed instructional materials. As the learners master these fundamental skills, the program will gradually progress to more advanced levels of reading and writing proficiency. The goal is to equip individuals with the ability to effectively comprehend and utilize written language for everyday tasks, such as reading and understanding signs, instructions, and labels.

Additionally, further studies can delve into the underlying factors contributing to the identified challenges, evaluate the efficacy of various intervention techniques, and examine the lasting effects of literacy initiatives on the personal and communal well-being of IPs in Panaytayan Mansalay Oriental Mindoro. These findings highlight the critical need to continuously strive to enhance literacy among IPs in the area.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Researchers obtained informed consent from respondents, maintained anonymity, protected their well-being, avoided conflict of interest, plagiarism, and bias in interpretation, and used results solely for research purposes.

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